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VISUAL AND AESTHETIC THINKING AS A COMPONENT OF HOTEL AND RESTAURANT MANAGEMENT CULTURE

ВІЗУАЛЬНО-ЕСТЕТИЧНЕ МИСЛЕННЯ ЯК СКЛАДОВА ГОТЕЛЬНО-РЕСТОРАННОЇ УПРАВЛІНСЬКОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ

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Гринько Т.В., Крупський О.П., Стасюк Ю.М. Візуально-естетичне мислення як складова готельно-ресторанної управлінської культури. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті розглядається феномен візуально-естетичного мислення як нової управлінської компетентності у сфері готельно-ресторанного менеджменту. Проаналізовано зв'язок між когнітивними стилями управлінців, візуальними кодами сервісного середовища та культурою лідерства. Виявлено, що дизайн простору, колористика, естетичні сценарії та композиційні рішення впливають на управлінську поведінку, ефективність персоналу і бренд-ідентичність. Узагальнено приклади естетичної організації комунікацій, візуального управління сервісом та просторової адаптивності. Обґрунтовано концепт візуально-естетичного мислення як складової управлінської логіки в індустрії гостинності.

Ключові слова: візуальне управління, культура лідерства, управлінське рішення, естетичні чинники ефективності персоналу, сфера послуг, індустрія гостинності, просторовий дизайн

Grynko T.V., Krupskiy O.P., Stasiuk Yu.M. Visual and Aesthetic Thinking as a Component of Hotel and Restaurant Management Culture. Scientific and methodical article.

The article explores the phenomenon of visual-aesthetic thinking as a new managerial competence in hotel and restaurant management. It analyzes the relationship between managers' cognitive styles, visual codes of the service environment, and leadership culture. The study identifies how spatial design, color schemes, aesthetic scenarios, and compositional solutions influence managerial behavior, staff efficiency, and brand identity. Examples of aesthetic organization of communication, visual service management, and spatial adaptability are summarized. The concept of visual-aesthetic thinking is substantiated as an integral part of managerial logic in the hospitality industry.

Keywords: visual management, leadership culture, management decision, aesthetic factors of personnel efficiency, service sector, hospitality industry, spatial design

In modern hotel and restaurant management, the concept of visual-aesthetic thinking is becoming increasingly important as a key element of management culture. Unlike the traditional functional-rational model of decision-making, visual-aesthetic thinking integrates cognitive, sensory, and cultural components of the management process, giving preference to imaginative thinking, emotional intuition, and aesthetically colored communication practices. This thinking manifests itself in the strategic design of space, staff selection, brand aestheticization, emotional presentation of services, and visual management of guest behavior [1, 2]. Aesthetics in management is beginning to be perceived not as a decorative superstructure, but as a way of creating meaning, forming a culture of trust, and a tool for building brand identity [3].

Contemporary research confirms that visual-aesthetic thinking is not only an element of attractive service space design, but also performs managerial functions: it structures staff behavior, strengthens brand identity, optimizes communication, and provides cognitive economy in decision-making. Through visual codes, interior symbolism, composition, and color schemes, managers can not only influence the atmosphere but also organize team interaction without excessive regulation or control [4, 5].

Visual-aesthetic thinking is formed at the intersection of a manager's cognitive style, organizational climate, and the demands of a new audience of consumers focused on experience rather than just service. Previous studies have already established that cognitive style directly influences management

decision-making, work organization, and the quality-of-service provision in the hospitality industry [6, 7]. In this context, the visual-aesthetic component is a logical extension of the cognitive paradigm: it allows not only to adapt management strategies to new realities, but also to transform management rationality itself, through cultural codes, design principles, and symbolic practices [8]. This opens sbecomesor a new understanding of leadership, where image, visual language, and emotional interaction become the basis for effective management action.

Particular attention is given to understanding the service space as a multisensory environment that not only shapes aesthetic impressions but also acts as a "silent mediator" between managers, staff, and customers. Consistence between spatial composition, visual cues, and leadership style contributes to improving the quality of interaction, reducing stress, and ensuring the predictability of service actions [9].

The main aim of this study is to clarify the role of visual-aesthetic thinking as a component of management culture in hotel and restaurant management, as well as to identify the cognitive, emotional, and communicative prerequisites for its formation and influence on leadership style, management approaches, and decision-making models in the hospitality industry. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to consider the following important aspects of this issue:

- to analyze how visual-aesthetic thinking is integrated into the management culture of hotel and restaurant establishments;
- to identify the cognitive, emotional, and communicative factors that determine the formation of visual-aesthetic thinking in managers;
- to investigate the influence of aesthetic ideas, visual codes, and design practices on management decisions, leadership style, and organizational behavior;
- to justify the possibility of considering visual-aesthetic thinking as a full-fledged management logic, and not just as a service or communication tool;
- to formulate conceptual conclusions regarding the place and functions of visual aesthetics in modern hospitality management.

The research used general scientific methods of analysis, generalization, and interpretation, which made it possible to systematize scientific approaches to understanding visual-aesthetic thinking in the management of hotel and restaurant activities. The use of the content analysis method made it possible to identify key theoretical positions related to the visual culture of management, environmental aesthetics, cognitive factors, and organizational behavior in the hospitality industry.

The logical-structural method was used to formulate the relationships between elements of the visual environment and management actions, which made it possible to construct an internally consistent conceptual framework. Comparative analysis was used to evaluate different approaches to visual communication in the management of service organizations, which made it possible to identify common and

distinctive emphases in the interpretation of spatial and aesthetic factors of influence.

Methods of systematization and thematic grouping became the basis for constructing an analytical table that reflects the main forms of manifestation of visual-aesthetic thinking in management processes. The primary sources were scientific publications in the fields of management, hotel and restaurant business, service design, organizational psychology, and visual culture, published in professional Ukrainian and international editions.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The growing attention to the aesthetic dimensions of management in the hospitality industry has led to the emergence of approaches in which visibility is considered an element of management logic. A number of studies have substantiated the role of visual culture as a source of managerial thinking, its influence on decision-making, the formation of service space, and the style of managerial behavior, particularly in the restaurant business [10]. Recent studies have emphasized that the visual characteristics of space, environmental design, and the compositional organization of service directly influence the formation of expectations, professional reactions, and communicative dynamics among both staff and guests [1]. Elements of visual organization – color, texture, lighting, geometry – are not only carriers of atmosphere, but also management codes that structure behavioral scenarios [11]. They exert pressure on the manager's thinking, forcing them to adapt management decisions to the aesthetic context.

These findings are consistent with studies that emphasize the key role of aesthetics in shaping consumer experience and brand evaluation in the hotel and restaurant industry. In particular, the appearance and behavior of staff (so-called "aesthetic labor") have a positive impact on customer loyalty and brand identity [4, 12]. Elements of service that have aesthetic appeal contribute to improving service quality, and their analysis is carried out through the prism of aesthetic theory, including autonomous, socially conditioned, and mimetic characteristics of beauty [2].

Research in the cognitive field emphasizes that the style of information processing influences the type of management decisions, delegation schemes, and the design of service procedures. Works examining the cognitive characteristics of managers outline the influence of associative and reflective approaches to interpreting managerial situations on the flexibility of managerial behavior [6]. In particular, it is noted that in the context of hotel and restaurant activities, the effectiveness of a manager is related to their ability to assess the visual parameters of the environment, operate with symbols, and, based on this, build the spatial logic of the service [13]. These characteristics are critical for adapting to a rapidly changing customer environment.

The principles of design thinking, which are being integrated into the training of hotel and restaurant managers, are becoming increasingly important. It promotes the development of innovative thinking

capable of transforming service practices in line with new standards and technologies that have emerged in response to global challenges, including pandemics [14, 15]. Reformatting the customer experience based on design thinking involves a deeper understanding of user needs and the integration of sensory and digital solutions into the construction of a new type of service [16].

The issue of cognitive determination of management decisions in the hospitality industry has been theoretically substantiated in a study that focuses on structuring the manager's thinking as a resource for effective action in conditions of service complexity. The emphasis is on understanding managerial thinking as a process that is shaped by experience, internal mental reflection, emotional context, and operational interpretation of situations [17]. Particular attention is paid to the concepts of cognitive culture, mental composure, content control, and the ability to reflectively inventory managerial actions.

At the same time, there is a growing need for visually oriented leadership based on the ability of a manager to create a recognizable visual image of a brand. Visual communication, manifested in corporate style, interior design, and graphic design of informational materials, serves as a carrier of organizational meanings [5]. Managers must not only decode these visual signals but also project them within the framework of a comprehensive service policy.

The external environment of the institution is considered not only as the design of the space, but as a management tool. The aesthetic characteristics of the premises, color scheme, materials, and details of the spatial composition shape the staff's perception of ethical and emotional norms of behavior [18]. The visual culture of the brand becomes a benchmark for staff, reducing the need for regulated instructions, increasing autonomy of action, and forming identification with the service model of the organization [19]. This requires a new competence from managers – the ability to read, design, and manage through visual codes. Other sensory elements are increasingly being added to the visual component, influencing the customer's perception of the hotel or restaurant experience. Smells, textures, sound accompaniment, and the emotional nuances of photographs in visual content form a lasting impression of service quality and influence the level of satisfaction [9]. Creating a multisensory experience is seen as an effective tool for emotional engagement and branding.

In a broader intercultural context, the visual-aesthetic environment is interpreted as a matrix of meaningful interaction between the brand, the customer, and the internal team. The architecture of the environment, typography, logos, menu formats, program interfaces – all of these act as synchronized channels of managerial influence that construct the cognitive and emotional framework for action [20]. The aesthetic design of the environment becomes a marker of professional culture, determining the level of visual competence of both staff and management. This is consistent with the approach that management thinking should be sensitive to the sensory context [2].

In contemporary management theory, increasing attention is being paid to the aesthetics of labor, particularly the creation of working conditions that value not only outcomes but also the manner in which those outcomes are achieved. Recent empirical studies underscore the importance of cultivating a motivational environment oriented toward the fulfillment of employees' emotional and social needs, in addition to their functional requirements. The visual and emotional appeal of the workspace is identified as a significant factor contributing to increased job satisfaction and the reinforcement of employee loyalty [21, 22]. Moreover, the digitalization of service activities, which accompanies the transformations associated with Industry 4.0, intensifies the integration of innovative technologies into managerial practices. Smart technologies, digital interfaces, and automated user experience design significantly influence the visual and emotional dimensions of service delivery [23, 24]. The implementation of aesthetically adapted digital solutions enhances competitiveness and enables the development of new approaches to customer communication [20].

The main part

The results of the analysis of sources and conceptual approaches made it possible to identify four structural dimensions in which visual-aesthetic thinking manifests itself in the management of hotel and restaurant activities. These dimensions include: the role of visual culture as a means of managerial communication; the cognitive-aesthetic nature of managerial decision-making; the function of the aesthetic environment as a management tool; and the formation of visual-aesthetic thinking as a component of managerial culture. Each of these dimensions has both theoretical and applied foundations, which allows them to be interpreted not as isolated observations, but as integral elements of a coherent managerial logic. The generalized structure of the results is presented in Figure 1, which provides a conceptual framework for further analysis.

Role of Visual Culture in Hotel and Restaurant Management.

Management practices in the hotel and restaurant sector are increasingly integrating visual elements as functional components of strategic communication, emotional interaction, and spatial brand identification. Visual culture, which encompasses interior color schemes, graphic menu presentation, visual service scenarios, and staff branding, is becoming an integral part of the management environment [1]. This approach not only influences the customer experience but also determines the style of leadership behavior, in which visual signals become the basis for regulating service processes [25]. Visual culture has a significant impact on hotel and restaurant management, as it shapes customer perception, reinforces brand identity, and defines the overall sensory experience. It encompasses not only physical design elements such as interior design, menus, signage, and promotional materials, but also digital media such as websites, social media, and virtual tours [2, 4].

Figure 1. Structure of the research findings
 Source: compiled by authors on materials [3]

Studies emphasize that an aesthetically structured environment has a direct impact on employee motivation and their involvement in the implementation of management tasks [2]. A space designed with visual and psychological factors in mind facilitates communication, reduces tension, and promotes the formation of a team sense of rhythm and pace of service [26]. In such an environment, the need for regulated instructions is reduced, since the visual structure of the environment itself acts as a carrier of normative meanings. The visual appeal of food, interior design, and even menus significantly influence consumers' perceptions of the quality of dishes and service. The aesthetics of hotel and restaurant photos determine the level of user engagement in the digital environment. The use of deep convolutional neural networks allows for the quantitative assessment of image aesthetics and the prediction of interest levels [9].

Visual culture also serves as a cognitive marker for managers, who form a model of action based on visual analysis of the environment. Components such as color palette, scale of space, rhythm, and symmetry of interior lines are perceived not only as part of the design but as indicators of the expected level of service dynamics [3]. A manager who operates with visual categories not only captures the visual aesthetics of the environment but also uses it to form a structure of management signals – from personnel selection to leadership behavior style [19]. Visual communication as a field of design is becoming an important tool for branding and strategic PR, especially for hotel restaurants, which are often not covered by general marketing promotion [5]. Effective visual strategies create competitive advantages, strengthen customer loyalty, and increase brand recognition.

This approach changes the very nature of managerial communication. If in classical models leadership is realized through words, directives, and orders, then in an aesthetically marked environment, managerial influence is also realized through visual signs – the symbolism of the interior, the design of work areas, and the graphics of informational materials. This transforms visual culture from a service tool into an organizational and managerial language

that establishes rules, restrictions, and even a style of thinking within a hotel or restaurant [8].

Elements of local culture, art, and decor integrated into the visual identity of a space create memorable impressions. For example, the design of the entrance, door opening mechanisms, and the transparency of shop windows have a direct impact on the customer experience [22]. These solutions actualize design as a management practice in hotel and restaurant management.

The latest digital solutions, including interactive virtual reality (IVR), allow for the optimization of behavioral interaction with the customer. The high quality of visual content, ease of use, and aesthetics of IVR environments directly correlate with customer satisfaction [16]. At the same time, inclusive technologies are being developed, particularly for guests with visual impairments, reflecting a new paradigm of social responsibility in space management [23].

Finally, effective personnel management in a hotel and restaurant establishment is impossible without taking into account the aesthetic context. The formation of professional culture, job satisfaction, and service climate is based on visual norms that are perceived as part of organizational behavior [21]. Modern management technologies must take this aspect into account as a factor of strategic advantage [20, 24].

Cognitive and Aesthetic Aspects of Decision-Making.

Decision-making in hotel and restaurant management is increasingly seen not only as an analytical act, but as a process that is sensitive to the visual and aesthetic context. The visual environment plays an increasingly important role in this process, influencing the cognitive dynamics of managers by activating not only rational but also associative-visual thinking mechanisms [3]. Visual analysis is becoming part of the management toolkit [27]: color palette, symmetry of forms, and visual cues in space are factors that influence the structure and pace of management decisions. These aspects are particularly important in relation to the organizational culture of the enterprise, which determines the style of decision-making [28]. When a culture of openness, trust, and reflective dialogue prevails in an organization, managers

demonstrate greater sensitivity to nonverbal and figurative forms of managerial communication. Cognitive processes encompass not only rational assessment of situations and problem solving, but also emotional and sensory responses to the design and presentation of space, which significantly influence the overall quality of management decisions [29].

In a service environment, particularly in the hotel business, space serves not only an aesthetic but also an operational function. It is designed in such a way as to visually facilitate operational decision-making by staff, suggesting the necessary actions or restrictions through composition, lighting, color, and the placement of objects [1]. Such visual "silent instructions" replace verbal commands, increasing management efficiency in situations of increased workload or lack of time [26].

Under such conditions, the impact of cognitive biases becomes increasingly relevant, as they may lead to ineffective managerial decision-making. For instance, confirmation bias, anchoring bias, and escalation of commitment are frequently observed in contexts characterized by limited information and time constraints [30, 31]. Mitigating the influence of these biases is possible through targeted training, the redesign of choice architecture, and the application of digital decision-support tools, including artificial intelligence technologies [32, 33].

Creating such conditions requires prior awareness of the relationship between the cognitive structure of a manager's thinking and the architectonics of the space in which they operate. Studies emphasize that the

higher the level of cognitive flexibility of a manager, the better they adapt to non-standard service scenarios, including visual variables in the process of analyzing the situation [2]. The aesthetics of the environment play a role not only in shaping the customer's impression but also in stimulating the cognitive processes of managers. The quality of the visual environment (servicescape) – including lighting, color palette, and acoustics – contributes to the enhancement of emotional well-being, attention focus, and decision-making efficiency [29, 34].

In environments where organizational culture does not support aesthetic communication, decisions are more often based on strict regulations and do not take into account cognitive interaction strategies [35]. The implementation of an integrated cognitive-aesthetic approach enables the creation of environments that are not only attractive to clients but also conducive to the efficiency of managerial processes and staff performance. This is particularly important in the context of increasing emphasis on emotional interaction, brand aesthetics, and differentiation through visual identity [36-38].

One of the key challenges related to the cognitive dimension of managerial decision-making is the influence of cognitive biases. In the complex environment of the hospitality industry, managers often operate under time pressure and with limited information, which amplifies the risk of erroneous judgments. Table 1 presents common cognitive biases that may affect the effectiveness of management decisions.

Table 1. Integration of Cognitive and Aesthetic Approaches in Decision-Making

Area of Influence	Cognitive Aspect	Aesthetic Aspect	Management Outcome
Hall design selection	Analysis of usability and functionality	Visual appeal, emotional resonance	Increased customer satisfaction
Staff selection	Evaluation of competencies, behavioral logic	Alignment with brand style	Consistency with brand identity
Service change planning	Analytical assessment of efficiency	Perceived innovativeness	Greater flexibility and attractiveness of changes

Source: compiled by authors on materials [29, 39, 40, 41]

Thus, the cognitive-aesthetic dimension of management decisions is not secondary but embedded in the very logic of the hotel and restaurant environment. Where the management culture is ready to accept the visual as part of management rationality, decision-making processes become flexible, intuitive, and emotionally accurate. The integration of these aspects into a manager's system of strategic thinking enables the achievement of a balance between efficiency and aesthetics, as well as between analytical reasoning and emotional engagement. This, in turn, enhances customer satisfaction, increases employee motivation, and strengthens brand competitiveness [29, 40, 42].

Aesthetic Environment as a Form of Management Action.

The aesthetic environment in the hotel and restaurant business is becoming a tool that directly influences the formation of management meanings and the modeling of staff behavior. The spatial parameters of the interior, the level of lighting, the zoning of functional areas, and the logic of their visual separation

form a communication field in which daily managerial interaction takes place [19]. A manager who thinks in aesthetic terms uses form, color, and composition not only to impress customers but also to increase the effectiveness of teamwork. The aesthetic environment is regarded as a form of managerial action that directly influences customer satisfaction, loyalty, and behavioral intentions [43, 44]. Spatial elements – such as design, music, lighting, colors, and scents – are capable of eliciting emotional responses, shaping positive experiences, and reinforcing brand identity [45].

In the structure of managerial communication, a visually organized space plays the role of an unspoken regulator of service behavior. It has been established that by changing the structure of visual markers – from lighting to lines in design – it is possible to manage not only the pace of staff movement, but also their level of emotional tension, awareness of priorities, and even the format of communication [46]. Aesthetics here perform the function of silent delegation – the manager shapes the expected behavior through the form of the

environment, rather than through instructions. This is particularly relevant in highly competitive environments, where the visually aesthetic setting serves not only as the face of the brand but also as a foundation of the marketing strategy. Aesthetics is one of the key determinants in shaping impressions that motivate customers not only to engage but also to further disseminate content online, especially through social media publications.

The ability of the space to adapt to changes in visitor behavior, seasonal cycles, and workload dynamics plays a special role. Adaptive environment design allows changing the logic of visual control, the balance between zoning and openness, adapting the environment to management needs without losing functional harmony [47]. This reduces the need for strict control, leaving the manager with the strategic function of building meaning through the environment. Researchers also emphasize the importance of a holistic aesthetic experience, which encompasses not only spatial parameters but also staff appearance, food quality, ambiance, and the level of service. The model of such an approach entails a harmonious integration of

four components – the physical environment, employees, the culinary product, and the customer – to create an emotionally complete experience [43, 48].

Research emphasizes that the visual structure of space directly correlates with the format of professional behavior of staff. Where the design of the environment is built according to emotional and tactile comfort, there is a decrease in the number of errors, a reduction in the duration of adaptation of new employees, and an increase in the interpersonal stability of teams [49]. A visually harmonized environment is a source of trust, intuitive orientation, and substantive stability, which are extremely important in the context of service multitasking. The design of the physical environment in hotels and restaurants plays a dual role – it not only shapes customer perceptions and emotional responses but also serves as a managerial tool for optimizing operations and guiding staff behavior. Table 2 outlines key aesthetic components of the servicescape and illustrates their dual impact on both customers and management decisions.

Table 2. Aesthetic characteristics of the environment (servicescape) and their impact on customers and managers

Design Element	Impact on Customers	Impact on Managerial Decision-Making
Color scheme	Emotional tone, comfort	Enhances staff responsiveness
Lighting	Atmosphere, spatial orientation	Stimulates productivity
Spatial architecture	Ease of movement, aesthetic satisfaction	Facilitates operational decision-making

Source: compiled by authors on materials [29, 34, 37]

Moreover, the visual aspect of management significantly influences the emotional perception of service value. For instance, interior design and decorative elements shape the customer's perception of price fairness, thereby indirectly enhancing the financial performance of the establishment.

The integration of aesthetics into managerial practice enables the creation of unique and memorable customer experiences, which in turn increases the likelihood of repeat visits and positive word-of-mouth recommendations [50]. Aesthetic design is not merely a matter of form, but a strategic tool for managing impressions, reputation, and consumers' emotional engagement. Thus, the aesthetic environment is transformed into an autonomous carrier of management norms and strategies. Design is not external decoration but serves as a structural level of management logic that ensures predictability of behavior, clarity of communication, and emotional cohesion of the service team [51].

Visual-Aesthetic Thinking as a New Level of Management Culture.

Visual-aesthetic thinking, which was previously considered an auxiliary factor in creating a service atmosphere, is increasingly acquiring the characteristics of managerial systematicity with each passing year. Its integration into the leadership model and decision-making style changes not only the aesthetics of space, but also the content of managerial culture. In this approach, form, structure, composition, color, and image become channels for conveying managerial

meanings, enabling wordless but effective communication between management and the team [52].

Research shows that in environments where visual-aesthetic logic has become part of the management culture, there is a more stable reproduction of staff behavior patterns, a reduction in adaptation barriers, and an overall improvement in the emotional climate [53]. A key role in this process is played by a manager who is able to interpret visual patterns as strategic markers and implement design as a form of managerial influence. This way of thinking allows for the transformation of familiar management models into more flexible, visually structured systems of interaction. Particular attention should be paid to the manager's ability to design a space in which management logic unfolds not through verbal instructions, but through aesthetically defined behavior scenarios. The spatial solution, which is embedded in the design form, becomes not a background, but a semantic framework in which employees operate [54]. Management thinking in this context manifests itself in the ability to "see the action" even before its implementation, predicting the results of interaction based on aesthetic intuition.

To capture the key manifestations of visual-aesthetic thinking as a managerial category, the table systematizes four areas of implementation: decision-making, staff behavior, environment design, and leadership culture. In each of these areas, visibility acquires a functional status, influencing the predictability of actions, the content of management signals, and the effectiveness of service (Table 3).

Table 3. Analytical Structure of Manifestations of Visual-Aesthetic Thinking in Management

Management Focus	Manifestation of Visual-Aesthetic Thinking	Expected Effect
Decision-making	Decisions are made taking into account the visual context and aesthetic scenarios of the environment	Intuitive decisions, reduced analysis time, emotional accuracy
Service behavior of staff	Employees' daily actions are based on the perception of visual markers of space	Stable behavior, quick role engagement, fewer mistakes
Environment design	Interior, colors, lighting are planned as a language of managerial meanings	Cognitive economy, structural orderliness of actions, reduction of tension
Leadership culture	The manager thinks in terms of form, style, image, and translates them into service policy	High level of emotional impact, brand identification, visual consistency

Source: compiled by authors on materials [52-55]

Thus, visual-aesthetic thinking can no longer be considered an accompaniment to management action – it becomes its structural core. This thinking organizes space, disciplines actions, sets the style of communication, and creates an atmosphere in which decisions arise naturally. Understanding this logic opens up the prospect of developing new types of leadership in hotel and restaurant management – ones that combine cognitive sensitivity, aesthetic rationality, and spatial intuition.

Conclusion

Research into visual-aesthetic thinking in hotel and restaurant management has made it possible to conceptualize a new type of managerial sensitivity, which is realized through form, image, composition, and spatial modeling of the service environment. Visual culture is not only a backdrop for service, but also an environment of managerial coding, in which decisions arise in response to visual signals, not just verbal instructions. Such visual-aesthetic thinking is not only a consequence of the individual style of the manager, but reflects the evolution of the management culture itself in the context of the aestheticization of organizational practices.

Based on the analysis, four main areas were identified in which visual-aesthetic thinking is implemented as a structural element of management:

decision-making, service behavior, space design, and leadership culture. In each of them, visual means play an active role in shaping managerial expectations, enhancing communicative effectiveness, and reducing the cognitive load on staff. This allows us to talk about the formation of visual management logic – one based on the interpretation of space, color, stylistic codes, and the compositional structure of the environment.

The results obtained are consistent with the position that a manager in the hospitality industry should act not only as an organizer of processes, but also as a bearer of visual intuition, capable of synthesizing cognitive strategy with aesthetic thinking. This type of thinking improves the quality of interaction with the team, allows for the prediction of service failures, strengthens brand identity, and promotes emotional stability among staff. This is especially relevant in the context of highly variable customer scenarios and visual overload in the service market. Thus, visual-aesthetic thinking can be considered an integral management competence that shapes a new quality of interaction in the hotel and restaurant environment. Further research may focus on the empirical measurement of this type of thinking, the definition of its educational structure, and its practical application in staff adaptation systems, visual branding, and service design thinking.

Abstract

In the contemporary hospitality industry, the integration of visual-aesthetic thinking into managerial culture is becoming a vital factor for ensuring effective leadership, staff motivation, and service innovation. As hospitality enterprises increasingly compete not only through service quality but also through the emotional and spatial experiences they create, the role of visual perception, symbolic communication, and environmental design has significantly expanded. This article examines how visual-aesthetic thinking functions as a structural element of managerial logic within hotel and restaurant organizations.

The study explores key aspects of visual culture that shape managerial decision-making, leadership style, and employee behavior. It highlights the shift from a purely rational and functional model of management towards a cognitive-aesthetic paradigm, where spatial composition, color schemes, lighting, and symbolic codes influence communication dynamics and service performance. The article focuses on the mechanisms through which visual elements support intuitive leadership, reduce the need for rigid instructions, and foster emotional cohesion among staff members.

Special emphasis is placed on the interaction between cognitive style and visual stimuli, as well as on the ability of managers to construct service environments that act as silent regulators of organizational behavior. The paper also discusses the strategic use of aesthetic environments to enhance customer experience, create consistent brand identity, and manage staff through non-verbal cues embedded in the design of service spaces. The aesthetic dimension of space is shown to function as a managerial tool that supports faster adaptation of new employees, reduces stress, and facilitates the intuitive execution of service tasks.

Drawing on recent research and industry practices, the article identifies four structural dimensions of visual-aesthetic thinking in management: (1) visual culture as a medium of managerial communication; (2) the cognitive-

aesthetic nature of decision-making; (3) the aesthetic environment as an instrument of managerial influence; and (4) visual-aesthetic thinking as a manifestation of advanced managerial culture. These dimensions are interconnected and reflect a holistic approach to leadership in the hospitality sector, where managers operate not only as organizers but also as visual strategists.

The article concludes that visual-aesthetic thinking is no longer a decorative or supplementary component of management, but a core element of organizational rationality in hospitality. It provides cognitive economy, emotional structure, and behavioral predictability, which are essential for ensuring service consistency and customer satisfaction. The findings contribute to theoretical understanding of aesthetic-based leadership and offer practical insights for designing visually intelligent service systems.

This research may serve as a resource for hospitality managers, design consultants, and educators seeking to incorporate aesthetic intelligence into leadership practices and staff development programs. The framework proposed in this article has the potential to support the transformation of managerial approaches in response to the evolving expectations of experience-driven consumers and the increasing complexity of service environments.

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